

Thermodynamic Studies of Molecular Interactions Between Picric Acid and Substituted Benzenes

BALASAHEB R. ARBAD and DATTATRAYA V. JAHAGIRDAR

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad-431 004, India

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Studies have been made on the molecular complexes formed between picric acid and substituted benzenes in CCl_4 medium in the temperature range $30^\circ\text{--}50^\circ$ by partition method. Thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° have also been evaluated which are utilised to differentiate between nuclear combination and dipole association.

THE molecular interactions between picric acid and various substituted benzenes and naphthalenes in chloroform have been studied by a number of workers^{1,2}. However, the effects of solvent media and temperature on these interactions have not been investigated as yet. In the present communication; we record the association of molecular complexes formed between picric acid and substituted benzenes in CCl_4 medium at three temperatures by the partition method. The concentrations of picric acid in aqueous medium was determined not by the conventional titrations but by the conductometric technique. This modification it is proved, gave accurate values of association constants. The thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° of the complexes were utilised to differentiate between the nuclear combination and the dipole association. An empirical relationship between ΔH° and ΔS° suggests the predominance of enthalpy and entropy of solution over the other contributions to ΔH° and ΔS° .

Experimental

Picric acid (A. R. Grade) was from B. D. H. (India). Carbon tetrachloride was purified by the method given by Vogel³. All the donors viz. benzene and substituted benzenes were from B. D. H. and were purified by the standard methods and their purity was checked from the boiling points. The thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) used was from Scientific Instrument Company Ltd. A direct reading Systronics conductivity meter ($\pm 5.0 \mu$ Mho) with 'built in' type conductivity cell was used for the measurements of specific conductivity of aqueous solution.

The partition coefficient of picric acid between water and CCl_4 was determined at 30° , 40° and 50° by the method of Moore, Shepherd and Goodall⁴. The concentration of picric acid in aqueous solution was determined from conductivity measurements. Earlier to this study, the specific conductances of various solutions of picric acid with concentrations ranging between ($2\text{--}70 \times 10^{-3} M$) were determined and a

standard graph correlating the specific conductivity with concentration of picric acid was obtained. The relation was linear up to $30 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration of picric acid, later on it had a slight curve shape. The concentration of picric acid in any unknown solution could be determined with the help of this standard graph. An additional check on the values obtained from the graph was made by titrating directly and also conductometrically an unknown solution of picric acid with NaOH. The agreement between the two values was fairly good. The plots of C_{org} vs C_{aq} (6 readings) yielded straight lines (correlation coefficient ≈ 1). The mathematical equations for the three temperatures are presented in Table 1. Association constants of the complexes

TABLE 1—RELATION BETWEEN CONCENTRATION OF PICRIC ACID IN THE AQUEOUS AND ORGANIC PHASES

Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	Equation
30	$C_{\text{CCl}_4} = 0.1923 C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - 1.210 \times 10^{-3}$
40	$C_{\text{CCl}_4} = 0.2149 C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - 1.148 \times 10^{-3}$
50	$C_{\text{CCl}_4} = 0.2340 C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - 1.000 \times 10^{-3}$

were determined by following the method of Anderson and Hammick¹ and Moore et al².

Results and Discussion

The true association constants of the donor acceptor complexes are presented in Table 2. Since there is no reference in the literature about these, no comparison can be made with literature values. In order to check the accuracy of our conductometric measurements, we have determined the partition coefficient of picric acid in chloroform-water media and then compared it with the literature value. Our value of K for the benzene picric acid complex in chloroform medium (0.089) is in

TABLE 2—TRUE ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF PICRIC ACID-SUBSTITUTED BENZENE COMPLEXES

Donors	Temp °C		
	30	40	50
Benzene	6.56 ± 0.02	4.98 ± 0.02	4.08 ± 0.02
Toluene	6.49 ± 0.01	5.33 ± 0.02	4.37 ± 0.02
<i>o</i> -xylene	8.22 ± 0.03	6.98 ± 0.02	6.79 ± 0.02
<i>m</i> -xylene	9.70 ± 0.02	8.20 ± 0.03	7.81 ± 0.02
<i>p</i> -xylene	12.42 ± 0.02	10.67 ± 0.02	10.21 ± 0.01
Chlorobenzene	11.73 ± 0.02	9.91 ± 0.01	8.92 ± 0.02
Bromobenzene	12.12 ± 0.03	10.64 ± 0.03	10.02 ± 0.01
Iodobenzene	13.87 ± 0.03	13.15 ± 0.02	11.59 ± 0.01
Nitrobenzene	13.71 ± 0.02	13.02 ± 0.02	12.39 ± 0.03

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR PICRIC ACID-SUBSTITUTED BENZENE COMPLEXES

Donors	$-\Delta G^\circ$	$-\Delta H^\circ$	$-\Delta S^\circ$
	K cal/mole	K cal/mole	cal/deg/mole
Benzene	0.82	4.61	12.70
Toluene	0.82	4.30	11.70
<i>o</i> -xylene	1.09	1.95	2.90
<i>m</i> -xylene	1.20	2.18	3.29
<i>p</i> -xylene	1.37	2.61	4.10
Chlorobenzene	1.30	2.58	4.30
Bromobenzene	1.37	1.82	1.50
Iodobenzene	1.44	1.69	0.80
Nitrobenzene	1.51	1.92	1.97

fairly good agreement with the literature value (0.09)⁹.

The K values are significantly higher in CCl_4 medium than in CHCl_3 . The methyl substituted benzene complexes follow the order: p -> m -> o -xylene > toluene. This order is followed in CHCl_3 medium also. Anderson and Hammick¹ have connected it with the fact that the nuclear methylation increases from toluene to xylene. Our values of K are in agreement with their observations. The complexes with halogeno benzenes and nitrobenzene show significantly higher values of K . In the series under investigation, the nitrobenzene complex along with the iodobenzene complex has the higher value of K . The nitro group being a σ and π -acceptor, nitrobenzene should have a lower value of K than the parent compound, i.e., benzene. The interaction between the components in a non-polar solvent like CCl_4 may not be a simple case of π -complex formation and may include such electrostatic effects as dipole-dipole interaction, dipole-induced dipole interaction, Vander waals interaction, etc., which may not be equally affected by substituent groups. It seems, therefore, that the higher stability of the complex is due to the inclusion of dipole association between the nitro group of picric acid and the nitro group of nitrobenzene, in addition to the simple complexations. In the case of picric acid, there are two modes of combinations: (a) nuclear combination and (b) dipole association. The nitro group in the hydrocarbon (donor), having strongly negative character, acts like the halogen to diminish the nuclear combination but increases K on account of dipole association.

In the series, benzene and toluene complexes have relatively higher values of $-\Delta H^\circ$ and $-\Delta S^\circ$ (Table 3). In the case of the xylene series, the order: p -> m -> o -xylene is also followed by the values of $-\Delta G^\circ$, $-\Delta H^\circ$ and $-\Delta S^\circ$. The magnitudes of ΔH° and ΔS° are low for bromo, iodo and nitro substituted benzenes. As a general rule ΔH° and ΔS° should become more negative as the equilibrium constant for complex formation increases because the donor and acceptor are subjected to more physical restraint, and bond becomes stronger. In the series, the nitrobenzene and iodobenzene

complexes have the highest values of association constants but their formation is accompanied by much low values of entropy and enthalpy changes. The lower value of ΔH° for nitrobenzene complex supplements the earlier assumption of diminishing nature of nuclear combination in the π -complex. Steric factor, on the other hand, may be playing a significant role in the iodobenzene complex.

The variation in ΔS° for a series of complexes (ignoring the steric effect) is primarily due to the change in $\Delta S^\circ_{\text{vib}}$, while the variation in ΔH° is due to the change in ΔE° , i. e., the dissociation energy of the complex. We plotted a graph of ΔH° vs ΔS° to understand the nature of relationship between the two parameters. All the nine points (Fig. 1) corresponding to benzene and substituted

Fig. 1. The plot of ΔH° vs ΔS° for the molecular interactions between picric acid and substituted benzene donors;

- (1) Benzene, (2) Toluene, (3) *o*-xylene, (4) *m*-xylene,
- (5) *p*-xylene, (6) Chlorobenzene, (7) Bromobenzene,
- (8) Iodobenzene and (9) Nitrobenzene.

benzene complexes of picric acid fell on a very good straight line (correlation coefficient ≈ 1). The mathematical relationship between ΔH° and ΔS° is given by the equation $\Delta H^\circ = (0.23\Delta S^\circ - 1.5) \times 10^6$.

The empirical relationship between ΔS° and ΔH° implies that $\Delta S^\circ_{\text{vib}}$ is linearly related to ΔE° . The only other explanation for the linear relationship appears to be the possibility that the enthalpy and entropy of solution are more important than the other combination of ΔS° and ΔH° .

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